

The activities of the first children's museum "In the world of miracles" on the basis of the State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: For the first time in Uzbekistan, the Children's Museum "In the World of Miracles" was created at the State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan. This children's museum is designed for children from 4 to 14 years old.

This museum develops children's knowledge of history, creating a basis for their interaction with the historical era. It is important that when visiting the museum, children not only get acquainted with museum exhibits and history, but can also take part in various crafts themselves, work in collaboration with other children, can also hold the exhibits they are interested in and try to make them themselves.

One of the departments of the Children's Museum is called "Young Archaeologists". In this department, children can get acquainted with materials related to archaeology and participate in trainings to increase their social activity. In this section, children have the opportunity to travel back to the ancient period of history, find coins, determine the name and period of the ruler's reign on the coin, and try out the oldest tools used by their ancestors. Classes of the "Young Archaeologist" section are conducted using the materials of the museum exposition. Thus, children can get acquainted with the Stone, Bronze Age, as well as with the period of antiquity and the early Middle Ages through various interactive activities.

In the section "History of writing and coinage of the first coins" children can get acquainted with the first local coins on the territory of ancient Uzbekistan of the Hellenistic period in the IV-III centuries BC. which were found in Sogd, Greek Bactria, Khorezm, and later in the IV-III centuries in the lower reaches of Chacha, Usturshona, Ferghana. They will also be able to get acquainted with interesting information on the history of writing and get acquainted with ancient types of writing: Aramaic, Sogdian, Greek, Arabic and others, there will also be an opportunity to try writing in different writing styles.

Specially organized museums for children serve as the main source in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, independent thinking, caring attitude to events and, most importantly, the formation of a sense of preserving their material and cultural heritage. Such museums teach children to conquer the world through play, creativity and communication. Since the educational process at the school is based on the curriculum, the learning process is somewhat limited. In the museum, on the contrary, children are given a wide opportunity to learn the secrets of life, full of various events and phenomena, and to study them more deeply.

The boundary between time and knowledge will be closely related to their will of desire. This, of course, gives children the opportunity to move freely, think and expand their worldview. After all, today museums are becoming the only miraculous place that mainly satisfies the interests and needs of young people, allowing them to freely communicate face to face with history.

Keywords: The State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan, "In the world of miracles", the circle "Young archaeologists", pedagogical quests.

The State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan is the oldest scientific and educational institution in Central Asia with over 120 years of history. The exhibits presented in the exposition of the museum testify to the ancient history of the eastern civilization in Uzbekistan. The museum also stores unique archival materials, manuscripts, historical documents, photographic materials reflecting the most important stages in the history of Uzbekistan.

Unique examples of sculpture, painting, pottery and glass art make it possible to appreciate the level of aesthetic imagination of the art of Uzbekistan.

Today, more than ever, great attention is paid to children's creativity. In many countries, special children's museums are being created, the tasks of which reflect the needs and interests of the younger generation.

Strengthening the family, through various educational programs that stimulate the curiosity of kids and encourage interactive forms of learning, contribute to the development and upbringing of children. Such programs are aimed primarily at pedagogical experiments, new forms of museum activity and the development of modern original methods.

Research results. A worthy gift for the 20th anniversary of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan was the opening of the first Children's Museum in the Republic in the State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan. The initiator of its creation is the director of the Museum of History, Doctor of Historical Sciences Zhannat Khamidovna Ismailova, who studied the experience of creating such institutions in the Republic of Korea, Russia and other countries. The Children's Museum, created by the efforts of the scientific team headed by her and designed according to the sketches of the chief artist of the State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan Kh. Yu. Umarov, is designed for children of all ages, from preschoolers to high school students.

At the entrance to the museum, children are greeted by fairy-tale characters: a beauty and a horseman in national costumes.

Bright, colorful stands with picturesque images of fairy-tale characters, children's furniture, from which objects can be used to make entire playgrounds, stools with carved legs, painted in different colors - everything is designed to create an interesting, attractive and comfortable environment for the child.

The museum has a variety of sections in which children can find activities according to their interests. For example, in the section "Young Archaeologist" there is an amazing opportunity to make a virtual journey into ancient times. The layout of the site of a primitive man introduces the dawn of civilization. A fire "burns" in the cave, animal skins are scattered on the earthen floor. The inhabitants of the camp left: the men - to hunt, the women and children - to gather fruit.

The next section of the "time machine" exposition - the diorama of the settlement of Kampyrtepa acquaints the viewer with the city-fortress of the ancient era, founded in IV - III centuries BC at the site of the crossing over the Amu Darya, 30 kilometers from Termez. The general view of the archaeological excavations, captured on the banner, allows us to imagine the layout of the ancient city, its houses and streets. Nearby are ceramic vessels, a hearth and other household items of our ancestors.

Young visitors of the Children's Museum can also get acquainted with the samples of writing that existed since ancient times on the territory of Uzbekistan and neighboring countries in various historical eras. Aramaic writing, Kharoshthi, Sogdian, Pahlavi, ancient Turkic runic, Arabic - and these are not all types of writing, samples of which archaeologists find on the territory of our country. The inscriptions are present on carved objects. The exposition of the Children's Museum presents enlarged copies of dummies of gems - seals with the image of a rider on an elephant and a Pahlavi inscription; a Kushan coin with the Kharoshtha script ; coins of Mirzo Ulugbek with an Arabic inscription; fragments of ceramic vessels with Aramaic and Sogdian inscriptions; a copy of a document from the archives of the Toprakkala Palace III - IV centuries; dummies of sticks for writing; a copy of a Sogdian document of the 8th century found on Mount Mug , and other items ¹.

In this museum, it is possible to make a "journey" along the roads of the Great Silk Road. The map of the Great Silk Road, which connected the countries of East and West, gives an idea of its unique significance, along the roads of which not only goods, but also cultural and spiritual values moved.

Models of coins of Ancient Bactria, Sasanian (5th century), Sogdian (7th century) with a square hole, Khiva Khanate and Bukhara Emirate (19th century) and other exhibits serve as the basis for the guide's story about active international money exchange. People did not immediately come to monetary circulation. Initially, cowrie shells from the shores of the Indian Ocean, as well

¹ Botirov B. The audience is sparse. // Essence. 2011 No. 20.

as bundles of metal rings, iron hoes and rods, bronze hatchets and copper ingots, participated in the trade exchange as a monetary equivalent.

Photographs of these ancient "money", which were in circulation in various states of antiquity in Asia and Africa, supplement the information from history textbooks about the Ancient World. Also, the child's ideas about the culture of other peoples are expanded by the samples of numbers used by the Mayan tribes in Central America, the ancient Romans and other peoples.

It is worth noting that visitors to the Children's Museum not only watch and listen, but also try themselves in the role of scientists, for example, archaeologists. Boxes with sand, shovels and ladles are placed next to the stands. Young visitors are given the opportunity to feel like a treasure hunter, find a coin hidden in the sand, and get another prize!

The children are invited to draw the exhibits they like or take a series of photographs of them. To do this, the museum provides easels, and you can also try to fashion a clay vessel, make a doll, embroider a national pattern. Such activities help children to better learn information about different historical periods and cultures of different eras.

Photographic materials and systematization of information about the exhibits can be used as an introduction to the methodology of scientific research. Sections of the stationary museum exposition are actively included in the classes. The children have access to the historical space, the opportunity to personally experience and comprehend cultural and historical distances.

In the "Young embroiderer" section, under the guidance of an experienced mentor, children learn to comprehend the secrets of traditional embroidery art. Uzbek embroideries enjoy well-deserved fame not only in our region, but throughout the world. Created by the skillful hands of Uzbek craftswomen, they adorn the expositions of museums around the world, telling not only about life, but also about the soul of the people. The whimsical patterns of Uzbek embroidery are a whole story about the history of the people, written with the tip of a needle. In the old days, embroidery was an obligatory part of the life of the Uzbek family. Every woman owned the art of embroidery, putting her dreams of happiness into it. The vast artistic and ideological experience of many generations of craftswomen was embodied in embroidery. In the Children's Museum, classes are held on embroidering skullcaps based on samples from museum collections, and not only ready ones, but also in the process of being made. Diverse, bright, elegant skullcaps, of course, will not leave any of the girls indifferent. And the colorful drawings on the work tables, which serve as a kind of instructions, will help to get to know the creation of each skullcap better.

The section "Young potter" helps to master the practical skills of the oldest pottery in Central Asia, to master the modeling of ceramic products using museum samples, the basic principles of constructing geometric, floral, zoomorphic, epigraphic and other ornamental compositions, to get acquainted with their semantics. Children enthusiastically work on the potter's wheel, using ceramic items from museum collections located here as samples.

During the tour, visitors to the Children's Museum get to know their native country and its natural resources closer.

A gazebo entwined with vines with ripe bunches hanging down (by the way, the vine is real, it was specially cut down in the yard of Zhannat Khamidovna and brought to the museum), with cages for songbirds, a basket and a plate woven from wicker rods, filled with skillfully made models of vegetables, fruits and berries, gives rise to a feeling of generosity and beauty of the native land. Keeping in mind that tactile sensations are very important for children in the process of learning about the world around them, the organizers of the museum made sure that the children could not only see, but also hold, turn, and examine the exhibits closer. Holes were made in one of the closed showcases, into which you can put your hand and pull out a silkworm grain or seeds of corn, cotton.

The section on the history of fabrics is presented with great interest and fiction, where not only cotton bolls, silk threads are presented, but also samples of silk and simple fabrics in the form of flowers, images of men, women and children. In this section of the exposition there is a special turnstile, created in such a way that by collecting individual parts of each of the tablets, you can make a national costume - male or female - of a certain region of Uzbekistan.

Unusual toys are waiting for the youngest visitors in the museum. For example, large cubes with numbers from 1 to 10 printed on them are collected in the form of a caterpillar. Magnetized numbers and letters can be moved on a special board, make sentences from them, perform arithmetic operations, draw with a marker. Nearby is a wooden train with a trailer.

The puppet theater with a bright curtain and a variety of characters is very popular with both children and adults. Even the carpet in front of the stage is made according to fairy-tale motives, as if a monkey, a tiger, and a bear were participating in the performance as spectators. The theater of the Children's Museum is unique: here the children themselves can try to put on a puppet show. And you can buy a doll you like as a keepsake. Each doll has its own unique, individual appearance and character, its own costume and jewelry, recreating all the features of traditional Uzbek clothing. They are made by the famous modern master of national toys from Khorezm Mansur Shavkatovich Kuryazov, a member of the Union of Theater Workers of Uzbekistan, the head of the puppet theater "Jaihun". The name of the master, a permanent participant of republican and international festivals of puppets and applied arts, is widely known not only in our country, but also far beyond its borders.

The Children's Museum has a library where everyone can find a book of interest, and kids can look at colorful pictures. The design of the library recreates the image of a fabulous town with turrets, arched window openings, lockers in the form of multi-store buildings, fences reminiscent of those that we see in garden plots. All this captivates with a variety of colors, a harmonious and charming color symphony.

In the library, children can learn the game of chess, which has been known in Uzbekistan since ancient times. Moreover, in an exciting way: the board is placed on the floor, and the large size of the chess pieces makes you move more, which is especially important for the physical development of the child.

In many countries of the world, a children's museum is one of the main forms of work with a children's audience in a specially organized environment. The Children's Museum performs the functions of upbringing and education: scientific (research), preservation (museum fund), recreational (cultural leisure). It is important that the children leave filled with knowledge and impressions so that they do not get bored. Here you can experiment, show and satisfy curiosity, work in collaboration with experienced mentors. Children learn to "read" the information contained in museum objects, undergo a kind of training for their social activity.

The organization of the work of the Children's Museum includes museum and pedagogical classes, master classes, exhibitions of children's creativity, cultural and educational programs. Of great importance are training and role-playing games under the supervision of an instructor. The museum includes theatrical performances in its programs, invites famous artists to participate in performances. Field excursions to the monuments to Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, Babur, accompanied by a story about the life and work of these outstanding personalities, expand children's knowledge of history².

The plan of the Children's Museum includes excursions to other museums, historical sites, visits to artists in their studios, to scientists in their laboratories; screenings of films, videos, concert performances, readings, courses and conferences. Conferences and symposia with the participation of curators and other specialists on various museum topics help to deepen knowledge on museum pedagogy for museum staff who work specifically with children.

In addition to museum workers, teachers, psychologists, and sociologists with experience in working with children are involved in the activities of the Children's Museum. Non-staff employees, who are artists, scientists, artisans, and other specialists, introduce children to the basics of their professions, the secrets of traditional crafts. Innovative interactive programs and exhibitions, as well as diverse individual and collective activities, allow you to combine learning and entertainment, contribute to the development of the imagination of all the senses and curiosity

² Gilmutdinova G.M. The Children's Museum as a Factor in the Formation of Children's Historical Thinking in the Context of Modern Problems of Museum Pedagogy (Foreign and Domestic Experience)// Site of the Institute of History named after Sh. Marjani AS RT (<http://www.tataroved.ru/institut/>). - P.22.

of children, mastering the basics of certain types of crafts with the possible use of the acquired skills in the future profession.

More than half of all museum programs are charitable: for children from socially vulnerable families, orphans, and the disabled. Programs for such children are developed together with psychologists and teachers using special techniques.

The Children's Museum is open to all creative initiatives. Other family members can come to the museum together with children. Museum employees set themselves the goal of creating a variety of educational, developmental, research programs, solve the problem of the most complete attraction of all categories of potential visitors to the museum environment. This will expand the range of museum services and make the Children's Museum an integral part of the educational, cultural, and creative life of Uzbekistan ³.

As part of the implementation of the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to ensure the accessibility of state museums for children and their parents" dated July 11, 2014, the Week of Museums is held annually on September 2-8 on a national scale. Accordingly, new exhibitions on various topics are organized in museums, galleries and Houses - Museums of the city of Tashkent and regions. At the same time, competitions, quizzes, round talks and master classes with writers, poets and artists, artisans, sculptors and potters have become traditional.

The events are widely attended by schoolchildren, students of the institute and university, professors and teachers. Organized events play an important role in shaping the feeling of love for the Motherland, respect for our values, education in the spirit of patriotism, and the preservation of our cultural heritage. It is also worth noting that during the Museum Week, all state museums provide free services to the public.

With children, you can go through training, which includes the following tasks:

1. Formation of an understanding of the relationship between the historical environment and historical periods through the monuments of history and culture.
2. Formation of skills and requirements for communication with monuments.
3. Development of aesthetic satisfaction and imagination skills..
4. Formation of a sense of respect, understanding and acceptance of other cultures.
5. Development of independent study of the cultural heritage of different periods and peoples.

One of the priority tasks of modern research is the role of museum pedagogy in raising children, developing their interest in culture and art. Through museum communication, it is necessary to develop an emotional response to objects, the desire to learn, receive information, accept and understand objects in the museum environment.

When evaluating the results of children's creativity, it is necessary to pay attention to the acquisition of the following knowledge and skills:

1. The opportunity to see objects of museum significance in kindergarten, on the street, in the house of friends or in nature.
2. Showing interest in museums as a unique cultural institution.
3. Master the specific language of the museum exhibition
4. Accept various forms of cultural heritage with enthusiasm.
5. Development of communication skills with cultural heritage: teaching behavior in a museum, skills for examining objects at an exhibition.

Children need to be helped to feel and accept the various bonds that bind us and our ancestors. Only then the lost culture, traditions and their meaning will have a special value for children. Museum treasures have an invaluable and unique educational impact on them.

Organization of museum pedagogy for schoolchildren. Analysis of visiting the museum by children of this age and their main factors of interest.

³Levtееva L. Welcome to the Children's Museum // Literature and Art of Uzbekistan, October 28, 2011.

- Organization of interactive excursions for schoolchildren aged 7-11 and 11-15 years old with a characteristic appearance corresponding to their psyche.
- The basics of having visual skills when working with them.
- Development of didactic games, developing exercises, creative tasks.
- Excursions with a monographic description. Important aspects of dialogue, discussion, conversation.

A visit to the museum by primary school students begins with the organization of regular visits to the museum and their involvement in the system of museum education. The formation of knowledge and personality of primary school students is carried out on the basis of two processes.

1. Direct reception of information
2. Mastering the description of objects or events.

The formation of the worldview of students of primary school age is regularly expanded and deepened on the basis of the knowledge they received at school. It is necessary to teach museum students not only to gain knowledge about the causes and order of various events and events, but also to keep them in memory, but also to independently find answers to the questions posed to them

For children of this age and in preschool institutions, it is necessary to organize excursions based on dialogic excursions, didactic games, creative tasks and developmental exercises.

It is necessary to explain to pupils of primary school age the attitude to museum objects, which are considered an integral part of material and spiritual culture, to pay attention to their place in world culture. Projects such as "A Painting in a Museum", "When Objects Speak" and "First Encounter with a Museum" can be used by students. One of the most important tasks of museums is the formation of the spirit of patriotism, love for the Motherland and service to its development among schoolchildren. Patriotism in every person is reflected in his worldview, morality and spirituality.

The implementation of the educational program in museums is envisaged in several stages. For example, before the start of the tour, the guide should first of all communicate with the children and establish friendly relations. It is difficult for children to fully understand the displays, historical words and processes in museums. Thus, museum educators must explain the tour by comparing, contrasting, or contrasting objects with similar objects or events.

Many museum teachers provide explanations to students in the form of questions and answers. This is also important in the reaction of young people to the events shown in the exposition and in the formation of their own personal opinion about them⁵.

In the museum, young visitors love freedom and independence more. For them, direct viewing and communication with the exhibit is considered educational material, incomparable with the study of copies, models or models of exhibits. Therefore, many museums make copies of exhibits for children in their rooms, allowing them to check the weight, size, shape and use of objects.

Conclusion. Currently, many foreign museums use theatrical stages. This is especially effective in historical and technical museums. These performances are manifested in the fact that a group of museum workers enter the image of characters representing a certain era, or guides change clothes in accordance with the theme. These scenes attract children and arouse great interest in this particular topic. Museums specializing in history have ample opportunity to work with various projects. For example, each object has its own history. It can be demonstrated to visitors not only from a theoretical but also from a practical side and create an opportunity for their participation. Pottery is considered one of the earliest crafts in human history, and by comparing its development process and differences, students can easily become fully familiar with the stages of pottery. It is also appropriate to show the place of development of pottery not only in a certain area, but also in world civilization. Of course, these clarifications should be carried out with practice, that is, with activities such as the manufacture of pottery and the determination of their period. Such training can

⁴ Zh.Kh.Ismailova. Zamonaviy museumshunoslik asoslari. Tashkent: Turon Zamin Ziyo, 2016. 80-bet.

⁵Yokubov Zh.

be carried out in such areas as embroidery, coinage, textiles, fine arts, typography, writing, the history of numismatics, which have developed since ancient times.

The museum not only gives students knowledge about the causes and patterns of various phenomena and events, but also teaches them to remember and independently find answers to questions.

In historical museums, which have ample opportunities for working with various projects, it is possible to present to visitors the unique history of each object, not only from a theoretical, but also from a practical point of view, creating an opportunity for their participation.

For this reason, it is necessary to organize excursions based on dialogic explanations, didactic games, creative tasks and developmental exercises.

Therefore, it is necessary to organize excursions for them based on explanations in a more interactive form, didactic games, creative tasks and developmental exercises.

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